

Reactions of diazonium salts with phenyl dithiocarbamate. Part-II. Formation of related arylazophenyldithiocarbamates

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Reaction of 1-naphthyl diazonium salt with ammonium salt of phenyldithiocarbamic acid gives 1-naphthylazophenyldithiocarbamate. Similar reaction has been carried out with several other aryl diazonium chlorides. Antibacterial activity of the compounds has been evaluated.

In continuation of our work on phenylazophenyldithiocarbamate¹, we report herein the preparation and antibacterial activity of some other related compounds, using aryldiazonium salts and ammonium salt of phenyldithiocarbamic acid (Table 1). Preparation of 1-naphthylazophenyldithiocarbamate is shown in Scheme 1.

Scheme 1

Antibacterial activity was determined against *Bacillus subtilis* and all the compounds were found to possess strong inhibitory activity.

Experimental

M.p.s. were determined using a Gallenkamp AZ 6512 apparatus and are uncorrected. IR spectra (KBr) were recorded with a Pye-Unicam SP3-200 spectrophotometer. For TLC, Kieselgel GF₂₅₄ was used and spots were developed in an iodine chamber or under UV-light.

Ammonium phenyldithiocarbamate (2)²: To a freshly distilled aniline (1; 0.1 mol, 9.13 ml), ammonium hydroxide solution (0.1 mol, 8.5 ml) was added. The mixture was

Table 1. Physical data of arylazophenyldithiocarbamates (4a-f)*

Compd. no.	Aryl	Yield %	M.p. °C	TLC** <i>R_f</i>
4a	<i>o</i> -Tolyl	85.0	142	0.47
b	<i>p</i> -Tolyl	81.0	157	0.46
c	<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl	88.0	140	0.52
d	<i>p</i> -Bromophenyl	84.0	153	0.50
e	<i>p</i> -Nitrophenyl	75.0	145	0.48
f	<i>o</i> -Carboxyphenyl	70.0	155	0.44

*All compounds gave satisfactory N and S analyses.

**Eluent: *n*-hexane-acetone (7 : 1, v/v) mixture.

cooled to 0–5° in an ice-salt freezing mixture and then distilled CS₂ (0.1 mol, 6.0 ml) was added dropwise with constant stirring for 1 h. The resulting white crystalline solid was dried (17.1 g, 92%), decomp. temp. 33–35°.

1-Naphthylazophenyldithiocarbamate (4)¹: To a cold aqueous solution of freshly prepared ammonium phenyldithiocarbamate (2; 0.05 mol, 9.3 g in 100 ml), a cold aqueous solution of equimolecular amount of 1-naphthyl diazonium chloride prepared by the usual procedure³ was added dropwise. The resulting solid red dye was washed with distilled water, dried (11.78 g, 73%) and crystallized from absolute ethanol, m.p. 148° (Found : N (Kjeldahl method⁴) 12.72; S (Carius method⁵) 19.70. C₁₇H₁₃N₃S₂ requires : N, 12.94; S, 19.85%; *R_f* 0.43 (eluent : *n*-hexane-acetone, 7 : 1 v/v); *v*_{max} 3120 (NH), 3040 (CH), 1600 (N=N), 1400 (C–N), 1200 (C=S), 980 cm⁻¹ (C–S)⁶. It was found to be moderately soluble in ethanol and chloroform but highly soluble in acetone. Compound 4 on heating with conc. HCl produced aniline hydrochloride and 1-naphthylamine hydrochloride. From the above evidences, the structure of the product was confirmed as 1-naphthylazophenyldithiocarbamate (4).

Similarly, other thiocarbamates (**4a-f**) were prepared by reacting ammonium phenyldithiocarbamate with different substituted aryldiazonium chloride: ν_{\max} 3210–3200 (NH), 3030–3010 ($C_{\text{arm}}\text{-H}$), 1610–1550 (Ar skeletal), 1460–1450 (N=N), 1350–1320 ($C_{\text{arm}}\text{-N}$), 1090–1070 (C=S), 940–930 (C–S), 850–760 cm^{-1} (disubstituted benzene ring).

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